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**Digitising *The Quarryman* 1913-1984:
Celebrating the history of UCC's literary talent**

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Abstract

The Quarryman is UCC's student magazine with over a century of history. Firstly published in 1913 and lastly published in 1984, it was a publication featuring faculty, Clubs and Society notes, literature, advertisements, and articles submitted by students. Its current successor is *Quarryman*, a literary anthology published annually featuring contributions from UCC's students, faculty, and alumni. Currently, *The Quarryman* is held in the Special Collections & Archives unit at UCC, but not much is known about the magazine by UCC's student population.

The purpose of this project is to explore the potential in the digitisation and digital archiving of *The Quarryman* to facilitate engagement with *Quarryman*'s historical significance in the past, and to create a valuable resource for future researchers who are interested in undergoing a similar project. In this project, I digitised an issue from each year between 1913 to 1950, totalling in 21 issues and approximately 800 items. I highlight the importance of FAIR principles in ensuring sustainability for data, accessibility to allow for a more inclusive user experience, and the rich textual information provided in the pages of *The Quarryman* regarding UCC's evolution as an institution and the cultural insights of daily life in a Cork City of the past.

Declaration

All work submitted in this thesis and the associated digital artefact is my own work and has not been submitted for another degree, either at University College Cork or elsewhere.

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“Students have been brought together from [...] various corners of the College to perform the task of publishing a thoroughly representative Magazine, worthy of a great institution, and worthy of the past records established by students who have made their mark in the big world we have yet to face. The result of the efforts of the present committee has been - The Quarryman.”

Editor of *The Quarryman* 1913 (Vol. I, No. 1).

Introduction

With the advent of a worldwide pandemic, efforts towards the digitisation and collections have been considered by organisations such as libraries, museums, cultural heritage, and higher education institutions as the right step towards accessibility for all users. In an environment where people are restricted from physical visits to view cultural items and objects, digitisation proves to be a valuable resource for institutions to facilitate the public's access to these items in a safe and digital environment. Institutions such as the prestigious Rijksmuseum continue to thrive during COVID-19 because of their years of investment in the digitisation of their collections. Even during the pandemic, the museum continued their digitisation efforts (FPJ Web Desk, 2021).

Here, digitisation refers to “[t]he process of creating digital versions (pictures, 3D models or audiovisual files) of objects in your collection and making them available for use” (Digital Pathways, 2019). Digitisation can result in a more accessible way of viewing collections as it does not require visitors to be limited to the institution's geographical location, while also enabling more intimate and immersive ways of interacting with the collections through digital technologies from mobile apps (*Media Guides · Senckenberg Museum Frankfurt*, no date) to tools embedded on an item viewer.

Alongside a rapidly evolving digital age, the act of digitisation is an attempt by institutions to adapt and facilitate engagement with their collections. The Internet's fast expansion and impact on societal life has influenced how we, as a society, consume and create cultural materials (Bertacchini and Morando, 2013, P. 60). Institutions that are reluctant in the consideration of digitally adapting to the changing cultural landscape may begin to struggle financially. This

sentiment is not novel either. As early as 1998, Smith predicts the future for cultural institutions that choose to neglect the digital:

“[...] [T]he online world is rapidly changing the expectations of the consumer and that whilst museums have an obligation to preserve the national heritage and culture, they also have an obligation to provide optimum access to their collections. Those museums that do not digitise and deliver online will lose market share to those that do and those that may have enjoyed a curatorial superiority may well slip behind those that read what the market wants and provide it.”

Through digitisation, we can also preserve items of importance in relation to cultures of the past and present. Part of the digitisation process includes creating metadata for each item, which can be defined as “data about data” (DigitalPreservationCoalition, 2018). The importance of metadata cannot be understated. Metadata summarises the detail of an item and its contents, enabling searchability amongst collections, acting as a snapshot of contextual information that proves useful for researchers, readers, and future archivists (DigitalPreservationCoalition, 2018).

The aim of this project is to digitise *The Quarryman*, a literary and cultural magazine which is a predecessor of the contemporary student literature anthology, *Quarryman*. Beginning publication in 1913, *The Quarryman* was a college magazine featuring articles submitted by students, notes from faculty, Clubs, and Societies, and literature. Articles featured in the issues ranged in a variety of topics from sporting events, interviews with UCC alumni and professors, and world events as major as the World Wars and Cold Wars. Evidently, preserving *The Quarryman* is a preservation of Irish culture in almost forgotten time periods. To some, a college magazine such

as *The Quarryman* may just be a look into the banality of student affairs. However, within this banality, it suggests the depth and contextual richness of everyday life in Ireland, often overlooked when chronologies focus on major events. Personal essays and even advertisements in *The Quarryman* allows viewers a glimpse into the past: What was Ireland like in the World Wars? How many of these advertisers remain in today's Cork City? What were students concerned about? How did culture transform over the decades, and do any fragments remain? By digitising *The Quarryman*, these questions and more can be answered. This project will look to examine the potential behind digitally preserving items of rich cultural heritage, and ultimately provide a means to access *The Quarryman* without the limitations of having to physically visit the Special Collections unit where it is held.

Outlining the Thesis

Literature Review & Horizon Scan: This section features a discussion of the importance behind digitisation of collections and items for GLAMs, with reference to the benefits for the institution, authors, readers, and future users. Additionally, it outlines the significance of inclusivity in digital collections, referencing the Web Accessibility Initiative (WAI) and Universal Design for Learning (UDL). Lastly, the Horizon Scan features a review of HEI journals' respective websites and their available archives, namely *Review of Postgraduate English Studies (ROPES)*, *The Ogham Stone*, and *Icarus Magazine*.

Epistemological and Methodological Statement: Here, I elaborate on the importance of the digital preservation and archiving of *The Quarryman* due to its rich sociocultural contexts within, which provides a textual history of UCC's social and academic history, which also extends into providing a brief glimpse of the culture surrounding Irish life.

Methods: I provide an overview of the decision behind choosing digital tools used to assist me in the digitisation process of *The Quarryman*. This ranges from the scanning equipment, editing software, and what was used to build the digital archive to home *The Quarryman* issues.

Process: This section gives further insight into the usage of the digital tools mentioned previously in Methods, alongside mentioning the challenges that were faced during the project from human error to glitches that resulted in the scanning process.

Findings & Discussion: I refer to all the steps and processes made during the project, discussing the problems encountered and my personal thoughts overall. Additionally, I elaborate upon what could have been done more efficiently if given more time and resources.

Conclusion: This section provides a summary of the project, what direction it could take in the future, and the potential behind digitisation projects for items in UCC's Special Collections & Archive unit for the purpose of accessibility and inclusivity for users and viewers.

Literature Review & Horizon Scan

Aim of this section

In my review, I will be discussing the main aims of the project. This primarily includes the driving principles throughout the course of the project from the digitisation process to the project's core beliefs, and what its end goal should result in. Additionally, this section will include a Horizon Scan which primarily focuses on journals similar to *The Quarryman* (i.e., Higher Education Institution journals) to provide an overview of what works most effectively in

the case of digitising *The Quarryman*. Lastly, I will be reviewing *The Quarryman*'s current webpage found in UCC's domain.

Preserving Culture: Why?

The COVID-19 Pandemic has led industries such as GLAMs to feel the weight of what life would envision with viewers being restricted from going to physical locations. From visiting and viewing a museum's physical collection or exhibit, to borrowing hard copies in libraries, these institutions must reconsider a digital transformation of their items for not just the survival of the institution, but accessibility for its user base. In this case, a digital transformation may be as simple as scanning a collection's items and providing online access. This in turn allows more users to immerse themselves because it is hosted in a digital environment. Additionally, it may enhance their viewing experience through digital tools as simple as a zoom function on high resolution images of artwork (Bertacchini and Morando, 2013).

Furthermore, museums and libraries benefit massively from these projects due to its potential to reach a worldwide audience. An exemplar of this would be the Rijksmuseum, which has benefited from early efforts of digitisation of collections and sharing them with users through an Open Data policy, meaning these digitised collections are public domain (*Open Data Policy - Rijksmuseum*, no date) The Rijksmuseum recognises the value in these digitisation efforts, as it has reached a larger amount of target users who avail of the open data services (Scheltjens, 2020). Similarly, I hope the project is able to provide a resource to not just scholars, but to a larger public who can easily access *The Quarryman* seamlessly through an online platform.

To further this point, Stauffer (2011, P. 294) states the luxury of being able to access old textual items in a Special Collections unit. This heavily relates to a number of items. Firstly, the storage of items in Special Collections requires a privilege needed for readers to access these items, such as being part of the institution itself (faculty, researchers, or students). Ultimately, this limitation prevents further scholars and researchers from providing potential contributions to these objects. Secondly, these textual items must be recognised as a valuable resource in order to be stored and preserved in such a space, which a lot of libraries base off of usage statistics understandably. This way of judging an item's importance means that we must undergo a loss of culture. Stauffer and their field advocates for a digital transformation with an emphasis on providing open access to out-of-print items (2011, P. 295). While this article is related to the problems of digital preservation in the field of 19th Century Victorian Literature, *The Quarryman* can relate to these struggles due to sharing some key similarities: its issues are fragile, rare in quantity, and held in a Special Collections unit. Like Stauffer suggests for their field's own textual items, *The Quarryman* should follow suit in being in a process of cultural transformation through digitisation and open access (2011, P. 295)

Furthermore, Stauffer (2011, P.p. 296-300) also provides a useful overview of digital library projects featuring discussions of their aesthetics, metadata, and page layout. However, there are no considerations of web accessibility in the creation of these digital libraries; this is something which I will certainly consider in my project.

Preserving Culture: Faithful Representation?

Similar to the points Stauffer (2011) made about the benefits of digitisation, Earhart suggests that digital libraries allow for fragile textual objects to be in an optimal condition (2012, P. 22). By

this, they mean that the digital manipulation and editing of the objects presents an opportunity to present them in ways that the physical editions cannot.

In this article, it became apparent that the concept of digital libraries and archives were not entirely welcomed in the literary field in its earlier days, even with its potential to transform physical items for the better. Earhart (2012, P. 25) discusses the lack of faith from scholars regarding the digital, claiming that the files in a digital format are “unsteady”, software upgrades may lead to sustainability issues, and the text becomes “malleable” in a digital context. However, is it not beneficial to have “malleable” text? The digital tools available provide new ways of interaction that may not have been possible before. The potential of the digital can become a gateway into more development in studies surrounding the texts, furthering resourceful contributions towards the respective field.

However, there was a valid point made by Earhart:

“As digital humanists experiment with data mining and visualisations, the treatment of the text is less about a representation and more about interpretation created through an algorithmic manipulation of the textual data points.” (2012, P. 26).

This point is one that I can agree with, however the potential with data mining is that it can provide insights and trends into the texts that we may not have fully realised without the assistance of machines. In my own project, I aim to have a balance between providing metadata and providing a faithful representation of the text’s physical dimensions. I will do so by using the

“Tags” field to enable searchability of each page and providing only relevant metadata for contextual information that is not otherwise available on every page (such as its change in publishers throughout the years).

Preserving Culture: How?

In *Digital Curation/Digital Archiving: A View from the National Archives of Australia* (2008), Cunningham emphasises the significance behind archivists’ efforts towards storing cultural material: “[It is] vital for ensuring organisational efficiency and accountability and for supporting understandings of [...] life through the management and retention of its personal, corporate and social memory.” (P. 532). Though I cannot fully provide the rich textual history contained within *The Quarryman*, I can at least use metadata accordingly to provide a searchable collection whereby users can produce their own understandings in the issues’ digital presentation.

However, I am careful in my own project with how I choose to carry out the digitisation process. Cunningham provides an insight regarding digital archiving: “Archivists document recordkeeping activity so that valuable records can be made available for future wider use in ways that ensure that their meaning and utility persist” (2008, P. 532). Hence, to aid my project I will create and follow a data management plan, with adherence to FAIR data standards. This will be fundamental to the sustainability of the project’s efforts and its lifespan beyond my supervision.

In the introduction of the FAIR Guiding Principles, Wilkinson et al. (2015) highlight the lack of standardisation amongst scientific data management repositories. FAIR attempts to fill the gap between differing standards, championing accessibility and furthering the reusability and

sustainability of valuable data sets. According to Skvortsov (2019), FAIR Principles provides a stable infrastructure which lengthens research lifecycles in communities. Here, the emphasis on sustainability and accessibility is a driving force behind the project's overall trajectory.

Regarding accessibility, the project will refer to the Web Accessibility Initiative (WAI) and Universal Design for Learning (UDL) (King-Sears, 2009) to ensure accessibility for all potential users beyond researchers. By following W3C's Accessibility Principles (2019), I can ensure that the project is inclusive for all, from content presentation, to user interface design, and comprehensible text. These standards provide a plethora of resourceful information, detailing suggestions of tools for accessibility regarding viewing of content, captions, web functionality, and ease of navigation. With reference to UDL, its principles are not just aimed at users with disabilities, but as a standard definition of good design overall (Kings-Sears, 2009). Providing an intuitive and inclusive platform nurtures budding research interests and facilitates learning for all users. During the creation of the project's digital platform, I will ensure that these standards are adhered to the best of my ability.

To conclude: digitising a collection reaps a variety of benefits for both authors, publishers, and readers. By adhering to open access in a digital realm, publishers can provide a more accessible means of viewing the journal, writers' authorships are given a much needed digital space, and readers are free from the financial, physical, and geographical restrictions of having to purchase a hard copy of the journal in order to read it, or travel to the location.

HEI Journals of Ireland

By viewing the webpages of HEI Journals, particularly NUIG's *ROPES (Review of Postgraduate English Studies)*, UL's *The Ogham Stone*, and TCD's *Icarus Magazine*, I can evaluate how each journal utilises digital tools and functions to archive their older issues. The functions used will be considered behind the process of this project.

This Horizon Scan looks to delve into each respective HEI journals' websites – particularly regarding the overall layout of the website and its Web Accessibility. Referring to WAI (Web Accessibility Initiative), Web Accessibility means making websites, tools, and technologies in a way that is designed for people with disabilities in mind.

In the case of this section, I am paying particular attention to the visual aspect of web accessibility: colour, font, and layout choices. To assist in a proper evaluation, I use a Chrome Extension named axe DevTools – Web Accessibility Testing by deque ('axe DevTools | Developer Tools for Accessibility Testing', no date), which runs a report on issues relating to accessibility standards.

However, the most important part of this evaluation concerns two main questions: Firstly, where do these HEI journals store their previous issues? What is the file formatting and how do they store their files? Secondly, how do they display their previous issues? Do they use embedding, plugins, or an external service? And how accessible, particularly in relation to UDL and WAI standards?

At initial glance, each respective HEI journals' websites share a few similarities. For instance, both *Icarus Magazine* and *ROPES* promote their social media accounts with external links to Instagram, Facebook, and Twitter on the website's footer or sidebar:

Want to Support ROPES?

Here is our [GoFundMe](#) page!

Figure 1: Social Media icons at the footer of the ROPES website (author's own image, 2021)

Illustration above by Aisling Ní Aodha for Issue 69.1.

Figure 2: Social Media icons at the footer of the Icarus Magazine website. (author's own image, 2021)

SUBSCRIBE TO BLOG VIA EMAIL

Enter your email address to subscribe to this blog and receive notifications of new posts by email.

Join 1,642 other followers

SOCIAL

Figure 3: The Ogham Stone website's sidebar, featuring Social Media links and a newsletter (author's own image, 2021)

Furthermore, both *The Ogham Stone* and *ROPES* operate on a more personal level by using the platform as a blog with updates of their upcoming issues, promoting works of contributors from previous issues, and literature related content. *The Ogham Stone's* posts include “poem of the week” from authors of older issues, updates for submission guidelines, and promotional videos featuring the editing committee:

OGHAM STONE VIDEO

FEBRUARY 18, 2020

The Ogham Stone Journal at Work

Figure 4: The Ogham Stone's introduction video, posted in 2020. (author's own image, 2021)

Similarly, the content on the *ROPES* website features book recommendations, announcements, and personal essays by the editing committee:

Students on Standby

No comments

Graduating has always been a stressful concept. Whether you are happy to see your university on fire in the review mirror or you're content in clinging to fond memories of badly heated lecture halls. Either way, it is a time of replacing old worries with new ones. Employment is usually the primary anxiety-causing aspect of this transition. Every year there are reasons to fear this graduation moment, after all, employment is a sensitive thing. Now, the pandemic is making everything rather difficult. The decision to move away after college and start the next chapter of our lives is deeply affected by a new conundrum, the whole working from home thing and the frustrating uncertainty about when this will no longer be part of the job description. We have been in this pandemic for over a year and we have all experienced missed opportunities, however, the altered working environments have directly affected student's decisions to move after graduation, especially if the move would mean leaving an area of cheaper (ish) rent for ... not so cheap rent. The notion of moving for work has sort of been removed as a post-graduation necessity, so students are left with a new question. Where do I want to work from home?

This is similar to the pre-pandemic desire to work from anywhere, anywhere now means any part of your sitting room because let's be honest freshly graduated students aren't exactly in the home office stage of their lives. And getting to that stage now seems like an impossibility because we are being held hostage in the space between student and working professional. During this transition, we are meant to shed ourselves of certain aspects of student life. Like midweek drinking and shit apartments, but alas I am weighing the pros and cons of, come August, remaining in my desperately obvious student house with my painfully obvious student hating neighbour because considering all the uncertainty isn't the devil you know better than the one disguised as a 700 per month room nowhere near a Luas?

Figure 5: Example of a personal essay posted on the website's blog section (author's own image, 2021)

ROPES (Review of Postgraduate English Studies)

Figure 6:: ROPES Home Page (author's own image, 2021)

ROPES is a HEI journal published by NUIG MA students since 1993. It is important to note that the proceedings made by its annual sales go toward a chosen charity. The journal appears to be partially funded by crowdsourcing, with a GoFundMe page available in the website:

Figure 7: A screenshot of *ROPES* 2021's GoFundMe page (author's own image, 2021)

ROPES' website does not display or archive any previous issues. This can be accredited as an issue with authors agreeing to digitise their contributions to the literary journal. Alternatively, this can be due to wanting to maximise all proceedings towards their chosen charity, as a digital copy of the current issue (2021) and the previous year's issue is available for purchase alongside hard copies. The digital copy is distributed via a download link which expires after 7 days of receiving this email after purchasing. Additionally, the digital copy is in a PDF file format, which can be viewed on any device from desktop, tablet, to mobile.

Arguably, this method of distributing a digital copy is not the best option in terms of accessibility and maximising proceedings for charity – for instance, author Cory Doctorow's first novel was released both in hard copy and a digital copy, with the latter being released under a Creative

Commons license. According to Lessig (2004), rendering a free copy online actually resulted in further physical sales as it acted as advertising and exposure.

In terms of Web Accessibility, the website is primarily a plain white background which uses the Georgia font in the colour grey, with a signature light blue (#a3c8dd) as a secondary or accent colour. However, running the homepage of *ROPES* through the DevTools Chrome extension flagged 29 issues, with 2 being critical, and 10 being serious. The biggest issues here include images not providing alternate text, zooming and scaling is disabled, and elements such as the navigation links do not have sufficient colour contrast.

The Ogham Stone

Figure 8: The Ogham Stone Home Page (author's own image, 2021)

Initially launched in 2014, UL's *The Ogham Stone* is the newest of the three HEI journals covered in this section. Similarly to *Quarryman* and *ROPES*, this journal is published and

produced by MA English and MA Creative Writing students. However, compared to *Quarryman* and *ROPES*, *The Ogham Stone* not only accepts prose, short story, and poems, but also art submissions. These art submissions may be important to consider in the process behind choosing file formats for the journal.

Fortunately, *The Ogham Stone* has a section in their navigation for previous editions, with the URL slug “/archive”. This page displays its issues with an accompanying picture of the cover, alongside a hyperlink. All previous editions are free to read, in a PDF file format. However, there are some minor mistakes in this archive section such as a broken link for the 2019 issue and displaying the incorrect link for the 2018 issue. It appears that sometime between 2017 and 2019, the Committee changed the hosting of these files from WordPress to Google Drive. Additionally, the 2020 issue offers Google Drive links to three available formats for the digital copy: a downloadable .pdf file, an iPad compatible .epub file, and a Kindle compatible .mobi file.

While *The Ogham Stone*’s archive section provides free digital copies of its previous editions, the overall layout and navigation of the website is not ideal. Running the homepage through DevTools reveals a total of 97 issues – 73 are attributed as serious, with 15 being moderate. The biggest concern here is the colour choice in the website’s elements, as 56 issues were flagged because of the lack of a sufficient colour contrast. Furthermore, compared to *ROPES*, the website appears more like a blog rather than a dedicated space for the journal itself. The homepage features recent blog posts, whereas both *ROPES* and *Icarus Magazine*’s homepages feature an “*about*” section which details the history and purpose of the journal.

Icarus Magazine

Figure 9: Icarus Magazine Home Page (author's own image, 2021)

Icarus Magazine is the journal that is most similar to *The Quarryman* – established in 1950, this journal publishes issues two or three times annually and accepts poetry, prose, drama, and art. Again, like *The Quarryman*, *Icarus Magazine* allows submissions from not just students, but faculty and alumni of the university.

Compared to the previous two journals reviewed, *Icarus Magazine* appears to have a solid foundation in creating open access to their previous issues, alongside utilising digital tools and social media to promote and display current issues.

Icarus Magazine uses Linktree, which is a bio link tool. Social media accounts or pages allow the user to display a link in their bio or description – by using Linktree, it creates a free webpage containing hyperlinks added by the user. A bio link tool is especially effective in disseminating information on social media as the user is only limited to displaying one link on their page or account:

Figure 10: *Icarus Magazine's Instagram account, with a link in description to their Linktree page. (author's own image, 2021)*

Figure 11: *Icarus Magazine's Linktree page layout, providing links to their three 2021 issues alongside the Icarus webpage. (author's own image, 2021)*

The magazine provides hyperlinks to their 2021 issues through Linktree, though issues from March 2015 until Spring 2018 are available in a text-only format. One important aspect to note is that it is interactive, instead of being static text to be displayed:

Contents

*Click on the contents to discover the work.
To return to the contents, click on the piece's title.
To read the contributor's bio, click on their name.*

Editorial

Nathanaël Roman, Cover: Inseparable

Featured: Trevor Joyce

Auto Intro

i.m. t.r.

Voluble Volucrary

James O'Hara, The Coldest Place on Earth

Figure 12: The Contents section of the Spring 2017 issue, detailing how to navigate the page. (author's own image, 2021)

The switch from the interactive page to moving the format to Linktree may be assumed to be a decision made by the Committee to offer a more accessible method of viewing these issues, and possibly because the webpage itself is currently undergoing an archive digitisation project, as stated in their About section:

Icarus is a student literary and arts magazine based in Trinity College, Dublin. We publish two or three issues per academic year and accepts submissions of poetry, prose, drama and visual art from students, staff and alumni of Trinity College. The magazine was established in 1950 by Alec Reid, and has been published with regularity ever since.

Former editors include Rudi Holzapfel, Brendan Kennelly, Derek Mahon, Michael Longley, Iain Sinclair, David Norris, John Haffenden, Maurice Scully, Sebastian Barry, Eiléan Ní Chuilleanáin, David Wheatley, and Selina Guinness. The current editor is Sophie Furlong Tighe.

We are delighted to announce that a full archive digitisation project is in its preliminary stages and that all issues should be available to access online very soon!

Figure 13: Icarus Magazine's Home Page text mentioning an archive digitisation project (author's own image, 2021)

The links provided in the Linktree leads the users to a digital magazine format of the issues, hosted on issuu. On initial glance, issuu looks to be ideal for digital publishing, with a searchability function and an immersive page turning feature when you click or press the right arrow key to view the next page:

Figure 14: Icarus Magazine's digital publication on issue (author's own image, 2021)

Figure 15: An older publication from 1950 (author's own image, 2021)

As mentioned previously, *Icarus* is undergoing a digitisation project. By looking at their public issuu account, this has been a project which started approximately a decade ago. This is an optimal case study for *The Quarryman* project due to a number of shared factors - the age of these journals, the fragility of the pages, and how to best preserve the past digitally.

Compared to newer issues which are digital born (ie, made in .pdf file format), *Icarus*' older issues do not allow any searchability of its texts which can be an accessibility issue. The reality is that being able to access these old editions is very unlikely as they will remain to be preserved in a library's special collections and archiving unit, with strict limitations on how to interact with these items.

	Basic	Starter	Premium	Optimum
	Free	€ 16 / mo	€ 34 / mo	€ 229 / mo
	Get started	Get started	Get started	Get started
Number of users	1 user	1 user	3 users	25 users
Published documents	✓	✓	✓	✓
Create shareable stories	✓	✓	✓	✓
Insert content on own website ?		✓	✓	✓
Customizable reading experience ?			✓	✓
Remove 3rd party ads ?			✓	✓

Figure 16: A few of the many functions/benefits detailed in issuu's pricing page (author's own image, 2021)

However, there is a major concern with using issuu because these digital publications must remain on issuu's servers. Additionally, in terms of sustainability, there would be no way of retrieving these digital publications if the company were to close the platform.

Furthermore, issuu can be taxing on resources such as costs. Certain features are restricted from users and publishers behind a pricing plan paywall. These include removing advertisements on your publications' page, and access to embedding issuu on your own webpage.

Regarding the website's layout and aesthetic choices, *Icarus Magazine's* web page performed the best out of the three HEI journals evaluated in this section. The DevTools extension only flagged 4 issues in total. The most immediate concern here according to the extension is that one element needs better colour contrast, and links with the same name have a similar purpose. Otherwise, this website contains the best features for Web Accessibility.

Quarryman

The *Quarryman* website is hosted on T4 (TerminalFour), the primary Content Management System used by UCC. Due to being under a UCC domain, the layout of the page follows a default theme to provide a uniform look. The website has not received an update of new content or posts since the Volume III of *Quarryman*, which was published in 2017:

Figure 17: *Quarryman's* page under UCC's domain (author's own image, 2021)

Similar to *Icarus Magazine*, *Quarryman's* volumes are published on the website in a text format, however it is static text. Each volume is divided into its categories: Poetry, Fiction, Editorial, and Notes. When choosing a category, the user will see a display of all available pieces under that category:

Figure 18: Clicking into Vol. III's link, then going to the Poetry section will result in this page (author's own image, 2021)

Keeping Web Accessibility in mind, *Quarryman's* website was flagged with 40 issues by the axe DevTools extension - most of which are moderate and minor issues. 21 issues refer to the page's content needing to be contained by landmarks. However, these issues primarily relate to UCC's default theme of buttons and links which are not relevant to *Quarryman's* page contents.

Besides this web page, the current *Quarryman* editors do not appear to have a dedicated archive section, nor do they use other external sites to host previous issues. At the moment, *Quarryman* remains to be a student publication which sells hard copies of their journals. Compared to *Icarus*

and *The Ogham Stone*, *Quarryman* currently fails to fully take advantage of utilising social media and digital tools to widen their reach and exposure. *Quarryman* is certainly a notable publication which features a long history of celebrating literature in the sphere of UCC. Thus, *Quarryman* deserves to have a digital domain of their own. By doing so, it provides easier access for readers who may be geographically restricted.

Epistemological and Methodological Statement

The Quarryman's contemporary successor *Quarryman* is in its seventh year of publication (*Submissions Open (Quarryman VII)*, 2021). Originally *Quarryman* was revived by UCC's MA in creative writing class of 2014/2015 with a budget given to publish hard copies for sale by the School of English (*Quarryman: About*, no date).

Figure 19: The cover of Quarryman Vol. 1 (Sprouls, 2015).

During its first year, *Quarryman* proved to be a publication that can cement itself in the foundations of the literary and arts scene of Cork City, with a presence in the Cork World Book Festival at the Triskel Arts Centre and Cork City Library (Southern Star Team, 2015). For sustainability purposes, future publications of *Quarryman* would be a collaborative effort between the English Literature Society committee and future MA in creative writing class students (Sheridan, 2015). Though this revival revolves around literature, like its predecessor, it is a celebration of culture surrounding the sphere of UCC.

At the moment, the issues from *Quarryman*'s predecessors are currently archived in UCC's Special Collections & Archives unit in the library. Evidently, this limits the number of viewers who are able to access the issues in a number of ways. Little is known about *The Quarryman* issues, highlighting the inaccessibility of these issues held in the Special Collections & Archives unit. This inaccessibility is also strengthened by the fact that as of writing, *The Quarryman* is uncatalogued. Even for those who are able to request an appointment to view these issues, they may not even know that they are held because they do not appear in UCC's library catalogue. In addition, the issues are fragile, with only 1-2 copies per issue. The conditions of preserving *The Quarryman* attempts to ensure that its history and contents remains available, but also results in a lack of accessibility in a variety of ways.

This method of sustainability may seem to be the best option for preserving one of UCC's cultural magazines, however, as an educational resource for researchers and history enthusiasts, there should be more ways to access *The Quarryman* physically and digitally. Through isolating *The Quarryman* in the Special Collections & Archives, the publication is sustained physically,

but not the culture itself if it cannot make itself known and to be freely available to readers. Therefore, by digitising *The Quarryman*, this project will go beyond the constraints of physical preservation of culture which ensures accessibility and further sustainability of *The Quarryman*. This project's efforts will open *The Quarryman* to a wider audience of readers, unrestricted by geographical location for viewing. Users will be able to freely explore *The Quarryman*. By extension, it provides a glimpse into the culture surrounding UCC and the greater Cork area and promotes the contemporary *Quarryman* volumes.

An aim of the project is to provide a pilot of a digital archive which adheres to FAIR data standards, keeping accessibility and inclusivity in mind. Another aim is also to delve into how to digitally preserve fragile items and objects in a way that is accessible and inclusive to all viewers. Lastly, following a data management plan will act as a blueprint for future institutions and researchers who may want to undergo a similar project. This plan ensures that every step of the digitisation process aligns with the core principles of the project and provides transparency for future researchers and scholars in the making of a digital archive.

The project's successes, challenges, and findings should hopefully be useful for future collections and journals, exploring the potential for sustaining, promoting, and providing an educational and academic resource for future researchers.

Due to the sheer number of issues held in the Special Collections & Archives unit, it would not have been possible to fully digitise issues from 1913 to 1984. Hence, I had an important task of choosing which issues to digitise. I chose an issue from each year between 1913 and 1950 because they were the oldest available copies in the unit. Older issues inadvertently documented

UCC's evolution, such as its name change from Queen's College Cork (QCC) to University College Cork and student reflections regarding the university environment. Furthermore, it also provides rich textual history through its articles about faculty, alumni, buildings, Clubs and Societies. For instance, UCC's Philosophical Society, nicknamed Philosoph (or Filossoff in older issues), has been established since 1850 (Hall, 2012). The details of their meetings have been thoroughly documented in every issue of *The Quarryman*, which gives readers a brief glance at a long-standing Society's past and its impact on the student population. The value behind these textual histories in *The Quarryman* should be recognised and become an incentive for parties (Societies, Clubs, or UCC for instance) mentioned to continue the digitisation efforts even after this project.

The project will give *Quarryman* exposure because of its digital platform. The rich history of *Quarryman* will be available to users in an inclusive and accessible manner, for both researchers and readers alike. This marks a milestone in reclaiming a digital space for UCC's writing talent, where users can celebrate the rich culture of literature that has flourished alongside UCC's own evolution as a valuable institution.

Methods

Before delving into further detail and elaboration, the table as follows is a summary of all the tools and software used in each vital stage of the project, from scanning, editing the files, digitising, and the vehicle for storing the issues:

Tool/Software	Its purpose
----------------------	--------------------

eScan Open System	Scan <i>The Quarryman</i> issues.
GIMP	Crop pages and colour correction.
Google Drive	Cloud storage solution for all the scans.
Microsoft Excel	Metadata for each individual page.
Omeka	Content Management System for <i>The Quarryman</i> 's digitised issues.
PDF24	Delete pages, rearrange page orders, perform file compressions, and merge files together.
XnConvert	Convert file format.

Table 1: Softwares and tools used in the project.

Scanning

In the early development stages of the project, the intention was to use equipment in the Digital Humanities lab. The DH lab has a Fujitsu ScanSnap iX1500, which scans roughly 25 pages per minute and can capture colour scans up to 600 dpi (*FUJITSU Image Scanner ScanSnap iX1500 : Fujitsu Global*, no date):

Figure 20: The Fujitsu ScanSnap iX1500 (fujitsu.com, no date)

However, the project originally included scanning the current *Quarryman* volumes (from 2015 to present). When the project shifted to focus solely on the older issues from 1913 to 1984, there was a slight oversight - the older issues are fragile, and must be handled with caution in the case of tearing of the pages. Furthermore, due to the nature of it being held in the Special Collections & Archive unit, it meant that using the Fujitsu ScanSnap was not a viable solution as I cannot bring these issues outside of the library's premises.

Fortunately however, the Special Collections & Archive unit at UCC offered a high quality scanner for use, Image Retrieval's eScan Open System:

Figure 21: The eScan Open System (escan.i2s-digibook.com, no date)

While this was not considered at all in the early stages of the project, it turns out that this scanner was the best equipment accessible to me - the scanner saves valuable resources (time and cost) as

it is free to use in the library, it is always set-up for scanning, and it did not require any hardware specifications from my computer. The Fujitsu ScanSnap required multiple drivers and hardware requirements, which my laptop could not meet, thus the eScan Open System was the most convenient and accessible for use. The additional features provided by the scanner include image processing such as curvature correction, fixing askew placements, and finger masking (*eScan Open System Book Scanner | Image Retrieval*, no date). Furthermore, this high quality equipment was ideal for the digitisation project, as it can capture up to 600 dpi. With everything considered, I ultimately decided to choose this equipment for the scanning process of the project.

Editing and Metadata

PDF24, XnConvert, and GIMP were used in the processing of the scans. The chosen softwares was used to ensure that the issues will be digitally preserved in good condition.

PDF24 is primarily used for resolving minor corrections to the PDF files from the scans, namely deleting pages, merging individual files, and performing file compressions. PDF24 is deemed to be the most suitable for this project because it is software under a freeware license, which adheres to the core principles of the project. Furthermore, PDF24 is consistently updated and has a convenient Help Centre forum with a small community.

PDF24 was chosen over other considerations, such as in-browser PDF editor services, such as PDF2go and iLovePDF. Surely, for such minor services, a browser-based editor would be substantial enough for the tasks required from the project, but the reality of these services is that they contain limits for file sizes and often require users to create an account, ultimately paying for a subscription fee for full functionality.

Other software considered includes Bullzip PDF Printer, another free PDF editing software. However, while Bullzip PDF Printer essentially provides the same functions as PDF24, it is software that is released under a proprietary adware license (*PDF Printer License*, 2015). Proprietary adware is defined as a software application that includes advertisements, which are displayed while the software is running developers use adware as a source of income and to keep the costs of the software down (*Adware vs Freeware - What's the difference?*, 2014). While this does not affect the efficiency of the software, the nature of the software does not align with the project's principles of free licensing and open access.

XnConvert's primary usage was file conversion, which includes converting from .pdf to .tif, and .tif to .jpg. XnConvert is freeware, which suits the project's aims of being accessible and open access. Other software considered for these tasks include SendTo-Convert (*SendTo-Convert - Vieas Web*, 2013) and Adapter (Macroplant, 2021), which are also freeware. However, after a trial testing of the latter two, there were issues such as unknown conversion errors and lack of knowledge from my end. SendTo-Convert did not provide enough instruction, which resulted in a failure to fully utilise the software. For Adapter, the UI was intuitive and simple, however every .tif to .jpg conversion resulted in an unknown error:

Figure 22: Errors displayed in the Adapter UI (author's own image, 2021)

Ultimately, I concluded that XnConvert is the optimal solution for file conversion as it provides batch conversions, filename changes, and metadata editing (Pierre, 2013). XnConvert also has a support forum which is still presently active with responsive community:

Figure 23: The XnConvert forum homepage (author's own image, 2021)

GNU Image Manipulation Program (GIMP) was used for any major changes to the scans. This ranges from the cropping, rotating, and colour correction of the pages. GIMP was the first consideration for performing these specific tasks as it is an open source software, created by worldwide volunteers rather than an organisation (*GIMP - Frequently Asked Questions*, no date). Additionally, it is the software that I have previously been familiar with, which results in being more time efficient with the processing of the pages. GIMP is similar to Adobe Photoshop, but is accessible due to being an open source software and the learning curve behind using GIMP is rather small because its tools are intuitive.

Storage

The data is stored via cloud storage and physical USB memory sticks. In regard to choosing the most suitable cloud storage solution, DropBox, Google Drive, and MEGA were the most likely

candidates. Keeping in mind the breadth of the project, the amount of issues needing to be scanned, alongside ensuring that the data will be safely stored for years after the project, Google Drive is the best solution. All three cloud storage solutions have payment options for increasing storage capacity, however Google Drive is preferred. This is because every UCC student has unlimited storage in their Google Drive associated with their student email account. Additionally, this email account is given to students for life, meaning that the data will always be accessible to me and is safely stored. Furthermore, Google Drive's sharing and editing permissions means that beyond this project, relevant people are able to access these scans without contacting me in the future: namely the UCC English Literature Society, the *Quarryman* editing committee, and the School of English.

Digital Archive

Regarding metadata, Microsoft Excel was the sole software used behind the creation of .csv files for all the issues in this step of the project. The other alternative considered for this task is Google Sheets, which is both free and operates online. However, Microsoft Excel was chosen over Google Sheets because of its offline functionality. Additionally it is a software that I have previously used often, thus removing any learning curve required for first-time uses of software.

For the creation of the online archive, it will be hosted on Omeka Classic over other solutions such as Wordpress and Drupal. All these solutions are open source CMS, which is ideal for the project. Wordpress is simple for beginners, highly customisable in regards to page layouts, and has 50,000+ plugins for use ('WordPress Features', 2018). Similar to Wordpress, Drupal is customisable and provides multiple ways of displaying items in a collection. Due to my own

scope however, the steep learning curve (Morello, 2021) associated with using Drupal was a major reason as to why I did not choose it.

The primary reasons behind choosing Omeka Classic for the project is due to previous experience in using it, and it follows Dublin Core standards for its metadata fields (*Omeka Classic*, no date). Ultimately, this aligns well with the aim of ensuring that “FAIRness” is adhered to in every step taken towards the completion of the project.

Process

T4: UCC CMS Training

Though the current *Quarryman* website under UCC's domain has not been regularly updated since 2017, it is a possibility that this dissertation project could be displayed on that website, under an Archive or Collections section. To prepare for this, I researched UCC's Content Management System and the process behind acquiring access to the webpage and also how to create a separate webpage for the dissertation project.

The process includes sending a website request form, considering the content of the webpage, presenting the website's architecture, and further discussion of the creation of the website. In the development stage of the website, they only offer the usage of UCC's T4 system (*UCC Website Platforms*, no date), which is not ideal compared to being able to host the project on Omeka.

Figure 24: T4's login portal (author's own image, 2021)

It is important to prepare for all possibilities in the project, even if this is not the preferred way of developing a website for the project. So, in the case of using UCC's Content Management System, TerminalFour, to display *The Quarryman* collection, I attended the mandatory CMS training provided by the IT Services Training Centre online. Additionally, I enrolled in their online course on Canvas, which is available to anyone in UCC from students to lecturers:

Figure 25: The homepage of UCC's CMS module on Canvas (author's own image, 2021)

The live training session is a tutorial on how to navigate and manage a website through TerminalFour. While Omeka is being used for the project, this training provides valuable insights that contribute to the creation of the Omeka site. In particular, it notes the importance of audience research and producing website concepts in the planning process of creating an optimal website which serves its intended purpose(s).

Contacting, Licensing, and Filling in Forms

To further the sustainability of the project, I contacted several key figures of the active publication, *Quarryman* - Dr. Eibhear Walshe who is a lecturer involved with teaching the MA Creative Writing class, and the 2020/2021 English Literature Society Committee. As a past Chairperson of English Literature Society, it was easy to get in contact with the Society Committee and I know the process behind creating the sub-committee responsible for editing and publishing the current *Quarryman* journal. With every issue since the 2014/2015 academic year, the sub-committee consists of the Society Committee members, alongside a portion of students from the MA Creative Writing class in the School of English.

By contacting these groups, it allows for collaboration between me, as someone who is preserving *The Quarryman*, and the current sub-committee of *Quarryman*, who are continuing the publication and promotion of the journal. By presenting the project to key figures, it establishes a certainty that it will be preserved and sustained beyond the domain of a dissertation.

However, it is ultimately decided that *The Quarryman* issues before its current revival will be digitised. The digitisation process and acquiring the licensing are predominantly the biggest factors to this decision. Digitising all the issues becomes a significant constraint due to all the steps involved, from scanning, editing, and creating metadata. This is unfortunately out of my current scope. Additionally, licensing is a big issue. The current *Quarryman*'s sub-committee operates largely from September until May, so being able to get in contact with them has been difficult, understandably. Furthermore, the rights associated with each *Quarryman* issue belong

to each contributor as well, which can be as time consuming as the digitisation process itself, as the authors consist of alumni, faculty, students, and anonymous individuals.

In the early stages of the project, I contacted Elaine Harrington and the Special Collections & Archives unit in the UCC Library for the scanning of *The Quarryman* issues and the copyright and or licensing required in the scope of the project. Previously to the project, I did not expect to be able to scan and digitise many of the older issues of *The Quarryman*, as there was no available information found when searching in the UCC Library's online catalogue. This also meant that I did not know how to adequately plan for how much storage is required for keeping back-ups and safely storing the files, and the time needed in the scanning process. Based on the annual frequency of publishing in the current *Quarryman* anthology, I initially calculated that there would be a maximum of 71 issues to be scanned to prepare for the work required. In my correspondences with Elaine and the Special Collections & Archives unit, they gave me vital information about *The Quarryman*. The UCC Library did in fact hold issues of *The Quarryman* from 1913 to 1984. The main reason why these issues were not able to be found in the UCC Library's online search engine is because they are all uncatalogued. The library staff were unaware of how many issues are published from each year, as they were produced on an ad hoc basis. Because the total number of issues available at the library may exceed the pre-calculated number of 71, this meant that the possibility of scanning, digitising, and providing rich metadata for all issues was out of my scope. I ultimately made the decision to scan only one issue from each year, regardless of the other issues available.

For the scanning of *The Quarryman* issues in the library, I filled in relevant details of which issues of *The Quarryman* were to be reproduced as published material for the dissertation:

UCC | **Library**
University College Cork, Ireland | Leabharlann
Coláiste na hOllscoile Corcaigh

Special Collections and Archives

Reproduction Application Form for **Published Material** for the reproduction of materials for **Research or Private Study Only**

This is a request for copying of materials which have not been lawfully made available to the public, such as manuscripts and theses. The request is to a librarian or archivist for copying on behalf of an end user who requires the material for the purpose of research and private study. This declaration is required by the Copyright and Related Rights Act 2000, and S.I. 427 of 2000.

To: The Librarian of University College Cork Library

Note: A separate declaration form is required for each item or article requested

For a copy from a periodical		
Journal Title:		
Year:	Vol.:	Part:
Author(s) of Article:		
Title of Article:		
Pages to be copied:		
For a copy from a book, report etc		
Author(s):		
Title:		
Publisher:	Pub. Date:	ISBN:
Pages to be copied:		

Figure 26: *Special Collections and Archives Application Form for reproduction of materials (author's own image, 2021)*

Shortly after, I was in contact with Dr. Aoife Coffey, who is a Research Data Coordinator at University College Cork. In the initial stages of planning and envisioning a completed project, I did not have sufficient knowledge in certain areas of what the work of digitising and archiving *The Quarryman* would entail. In our meetings, Dr. Coffey provided valuable information and suggestions which are now core aspects that drive the project. She recommended creating a Data

Management Plan to ensure that each step of the project is a building block to creating a coherent and comprehensive end result: Creating a collection of *The Quarryman*'s older issues, digitised and archived correctly for accessibility and sustainability. These meetings provided clarity for both myself, my capabilities, and what is the realistic outcome of the project.

Scanning *The Quarryman*:

I began scanning issues of *The Quarryman* in UCC's Special Collections unit. Originally, the scanning would include the current *Quarryman* journal, but it was ultimately decided that the older issues would be the priority, as including the current journal would result in a much wider scope. Additionally, *The Quarryman* had multiple issues from each year - instead of scanning all issues from one academic year, only one issue would be selected out of a possible seven issues. Preferably, the first issue (the December issue) of the volume would be scanned. However, the selection process prioritises the quality and availability of the issues at the Special Collections & Archive unit, hence why there are scanned issues from January, March, June, and so on.

In the first initial uses of the scanning equipment, it was quite evident that there is a small learning curve with properly utilising the equipment - proper care was needed to protect the quality of older issues which are more prone to wear and tear. Furthermore, I eventually learned to find the perfect combination of functions available on the equipment which simultaneously provides a more efficient output of scans with better quality too.

The issues were scanned with a 300 dpi setting with colour. The equipment offers 144 dpi, 300 dpi, and 600 dpi. Scanning in 144 dpi was a possible choice, however the quality may be too poor in comparison to scanning the issues in 300 dpi. Additionally, scanning in 300 dpi gives me

the option to reduce the quality, whereas 144 dpi resolution scans cannot be improved. Because of choosing to scan in full colour and 300 dpi resolution, the file sizes are considerably large ranging from 70 to 140 MBs per issue scanned. These file sizes will be compressed in the processing and editing segment of the project.

When scanning the first batch of issues (1913-1932), I believed that the best method of output scans would be individual .pdf files, which would later be renamed as their own page number. However, I soon realised that it was an additional task as these individual .pdf files did not save in the proper order. In hindsight, this was not time efficient nor convenient either. Evidently from the 1933 issue onwards, scans would be collated into a multi-page .pdf file instead. This solved the problem of rearranging individual pages into the correct order and overall made the scanning process much more efficient.

Editing Scans

After scanning the issues, the .pdf files are evaluated for any mistakes occurred by either human error or a glitch in the scanning equipment. The only software that is used in the editing process of the project is PDF24, a free software. I chose this software because it is accessible (no costs) and provides multiple functions for manipulating .pdf files from collating files, file size compression, web optimisation for .pdf files, and .pdf OCR:

Figure 27: PDF24 software's homescreen (author's own image, 2021)

Glitches regularly occurred in the scanning process because of the equipment - oftentimes if these errors were not spotted and deleted during the scanning session, they would be detected when reviewing the .pdf files when I upload them to the Google Drive cloud storage:

Figure 28: An example from the 1962 issue of a common glitch in the scanning process (author's own image, 2021)

The most common glitches in the scans were partially completed scans, or a scan which only features the top left corner of the page. When the glitches did not relate to the equipment itself, it would be scans with human errors. My hand would occasionally cover a section of the page during the scanning process:

Figure 29: A human error during the scanning process for the Spring 1952 issue (author's own image, 2021)

These glitches and human errors are a common occurrence in the manual scanning process, which was something that I was hyper aware of during the project. Human errors can especially be looked over, preventing users to fully avail of a book's contents. For instance, even large institutions who undergo a mass digitisation project such as Google Books can neglect its scan quality ranging from page obstructions, glitches such as warping or blurring, and sudden changes

in colour (Goldsmith, 2013), as documented in Krissy Wilson’s collection (*THE ART OF GOOGLE BOOKS KRISSY WILSON*, 2012):

Figure 30: Wilson’s collection hosted on Tumblr (2012) (author’s own image, 2021)

During my project, when glitches occur in scanning sessions, I immediately rescan and take note of what page(s) need to be removed in the review process, which normally occurs post-scanning. These were easily removed through PDF24’s organise PDF and rearranging pages function.

In addition to rearranging pages and ensuring that scans did not contain any glitches or human errors which would dampen its quality, I cropped the raw scanned pages through GIMP’s tools:

Figure 31: Comparison between a raw scan versus a cropped scan in the post-scan processing (author's own image, 2021)

Especially in the case of scanning from hardback anthologies with a large number of pages, the scanning equipment's AI would include pages that jut out from behind the pages displayed for scanning. By cropping the pages, it provides a "cleaner" looking scan which would solely display the page itself. This step may not have been a necessary one, but ultimately I believe that this is entirely beneficial to the preservation of *The Quarryman* and to the users that view these issues.

One problem that I did not account for related to the scanning equipment itself. In my third scanning session, the scans of the pages had a yellow tint. Initially, I thought that this was due to the equipment needing to "warm up", but the entire session's output all contained the same yellow tint. I attempted to adjust through the equipment's luminosity and brightness settings so it

would not have to be fixed during the post-scanning process. Unfortunately, it did not entirely solve the issue, thus I had to provide colour correction in GIMP:

Figure 32: A side-by-side comparison between a raw scanned page versus a colour corrected and cropped page from the 1933 issue (author's own image, 2021)

During the colour correction of the scans affected by the yellow tint error in the scanner, I also slightly sharpened and added more contrast in order to make the letters easier to read. Older issues of *The Quarryman* occasionally contained printing errors, either from the time of publishing or eventual wear and tear. This resulted in faded words on some pages, which makes it harder to read. Though this was a time costly task, similarly to the cropping of pages, it provides a solid foundation for the resourcefulness of the project for future researchers.

Storage, Formats, and Naming

When preparing the dissertation project, I originally thought that UCC's Special Collections unit's scanning equipment would allow multiple output destinations such as cloud storage, USB memory sticks, and email. However, the scanner allows USB memory sticks to be the only

option available. While this was not the scenario in mind when preparing to scan the issues, it turns out that it was the ideal solution - while the files are uploaded onto an unlimited Google Drive storage, the USB memory sticks will become the back-up storage of the project. By providing both a physical and digital storage, this addresses any risks or issues with these files in future, such as bit rot, human error, or even natural disaster.

According to Todd (2009), there are five main criteria for file format selection. In the case of *The Quarryman*, the most important criterias are adoption, which is the extent to which the use of a format is widespread, and transparency, which is how readily a file can be identified and its contents checked by the user. Finally, the last important criteria for the project would be robustness: is the format chosen inherently simple? Due to the core principles of sustainability and accessibility, I ultimately chose to use the .pdf file format for *The Quarryman* scans. The .pdf file format prevents any digital obsolescence because it remains to be widely used for the preservation of information such as official documents, academic publications, and eBilling (Fanning, 2017). Additionally, .pdf has a standardised format (ISO 32000-1) for digital documents and can be fully searchable which is exemplary for the project's goals.

While the .pdf file format contains many suitable functions and performs well under the criteria for the project, I did not consider the possibility of the cons with a large .pdf file size. This considerably slows down the uploading of all issues on the Omeka site, alongside needing to increase the storage space needed to safely store the digitised issues. As a safety precaution, I used XnConvert to reformat the .pdf files into .tif files for preservation purposes, and then converted the files into .jpg files for display purposes on Omeka.

By converting *The Quarryman's* pages into .jpg files, uploading all the files onto Omeka was highly time efficient and cut down the load time that was previously required when viewing a .pdf file of *The Quarryman* issues. This also solved the issue regarding needing storage space to store *The Quarryman* on Omeka.

In regard to the action of naming files, I made sure that I kept accessibility in mind - both the user and computer will be able to read it without any major problem. By adhering to Digital Preservation Coalition's basic guidelines to file naming (DigitalPreservationCoalition, 2018a), the .pdf file names of *The Quarryman* issues will be short but descriptive enough, use dashes or underscores instead of spaces, and use ISO 8601:2004 standard format for dating (YYYYMMDD) when possible. This will ensure the sustainability of the project beyond my own work - where future contributors can easily access and understand what has been currently produced from this project.

Digital Archive: Metadata

The compilation of metadata happened shortly after the scanning and editing process of the issues. Here, there were two options considered: firstly, compile metadata of each issue as a

Title	Source	Publisher	Rights	File	Tags
The Quarryman 1950: Page 1	Special Collections & Archives	The Kerryman,	Special Collections & Archives	1950-Apr-v3 (1).jpg	1950, Front Cover
The Quarryman 1950: Page 2	Special Collections & Archives	The Kerryman,	Special Collections & Archives	1950-Apr-v3 (2).jpg	1950, Advertisement, Queen's Old Castle, Jerh. O'Connor & Sons
The Quarryman 1950: Page 3	Special Collections & Archives	The Kerryman,	Special Collections & Archives	1950-Apr-v3 (3).jpg	1950, Thomas Crosbie & Co., Advertisement
The Quarryman 1950: Page 4	Special Collections & Archives	The Kerryman,	Special Collections & Archives	1950-Apr-v3 (4).jpg	1950, Advertisement, T. A. Falvey, R. Cronin's, T. L. Egan & Co.
The Quarryman 1950: Page 5	Special Collections & Archives	The Kerryman,	Special Collections & Archives	1950-Apr-v3 (5).jpg	1950, Editorial
The Quarryman 1950: Page 6	Special Collections & Archives	The Kerryman,	Special Collections & Archives	1950-Apr-v3 (6).jpg	1950, Editorial
The Quarryman 1950: Page 7	Special Collections & Archives	The Kerryman,	Special Collections & Archives	1950-Apr-v3 (7).jpg	1950, Editorial, Advertisement, D. Finbarr Murphy
The Quarryman 1950: Page 8	Special Collections & Archives	The Kerryman,	Special Collections & Archives	1950-Apr-v3 (8).jpg	1950, Poetry
The Quarryman 1950: Page 9	Special Collections & Archives	The Kerryman,	Special Collections & Archives	1950-Apr-v3 (9).jpg	1950, Poetry, Advertisement, Beamish
The Quarryman 1950: Page 10	Special Collections & Archives	The Kerryman,	Special Collections & Archives	1950-Apr-v3 (10).jpg	1950, Poetry
The Quarryman 1950: Page 11	Special Collections & Archives	The Kerryman,	Special Collections & Archives	1950-Apr-v3 (11).jpg	1950, Fiction
The Quarryman 1950: Page 12	Special Collections & Archives	The Kerryman,	Special Collections & Archives	1950-Apr-v3 (12).jpg	1950, Fiction, Poetry
The Quarryman 1950: Page 13	Special Collections & Archives	The Kerryman,	Special Collections & Archives	1950-Apr-v3 (13).jpg	1950, Article
The Quarryman 1950: Page 14	Special Collections & Archives	The Kerryman,	Special Collections & Archives	1950-Apr-v3 (14).jpg	1950, Poetry, Illustration
The Quarryman 1950: Page 15	Special Collections & Archives	The Kerryman,	Special Collections & Archives	1950-Apr-v3 (15).jpg	1950, Article, Poetry
The Quarryman 1950: Page 16	Special Collections & Archives	The Kerryman,	Special Collections & Archives	1950-Apr-v3 (16).jpg	1950, Poetry, Illustration
The Quarryman 1950: Page 17	Special Collections & Archives	The Kerryman,	Special Collections & Archives	1950-Apr-v3 (17).jpg	1950, Advertisement, Cornelius O'Keefe & Co., The Green Door, Liam P. Johnson Chemist
The Quarryman 1950: Page 18	Special Collections & Archives	The Kerryman,	Special Collections & Archives	1950-Apr-v3 (18).jpg	1950, Article,
The Quarryman 1950: Page 19	Special Collections & Archives	The Kerryman,	Special Collections & Archives	1950-Apr-v3 (19).jpg	1950, Poetry, Advertisement, H-I-B
The Quarryman 1950: Page 20	Special Collections & Archives	The Kerryman,	Special Collections & Archives	1950-Apr-v3 (20).jpg	1950, Poetry, Advertisement, Pope Bros.
The Quarryman 1950: Page 21	Special Collections & Archives	The Kerryman,	Special Collections & Archives	1950-Apr-v3 (21).jpg	1950, Article, Advertisement, Royal Typewriters
The Quarryman 1950: Page 22	Special Collections & Archives	The Kerryman,	Special Collections & Archives	1950-Apr-v3 (22).jpg	1950, Article, Poetry
The Quarryman 1950: Page 23	Special Collections & Archives	The Kerryman,	Special Collections & Archives	1950-Apr-v3 (23).jpg	1950, Poetry, Advertisement, Brown's Taxis
The Quarryman 1950: Page 24	Special Collections & Archives	The Kerryman,	Special Collections & Archives	1950-Apr-v3 (24).jpg	1950, Fiction
The Quarryman 1950: Page 25	Special Collections & Archives	The Kerryman,	Special Collections & Archives	1950-Apr-v3 (25).jpg	1950, Clubs, Athletics, Boxing
The Quarryman 1950: Page 26	Special Collections & Archives	The Kerryman,	Special Collections & Archives	1950-Apr-v3 (26).jpg	1950, Advertisement, Presentation Brothers College, Grants, D. & A. O'Leary, Jawa and Cz
The Quarryman 1950: Page 27	Special Collections & Archives	The Kerryman,	Special Collections & Archives	1950-Apr-v3 (27).jpg	1950, Clubs, Chess, Rowing, Hockey

single item, or secondly, compile metadata of each individual page from each issue. Evidently, both options present their pros and cons. The first option would be much more time efficient, but the metadata will have to encompass the entirety of the issue rather than each individual page. Ultimately, I decided to compile metadata for each individual page to provide a much better means of searchability for users that may view it in the future. Because of this however, it meant that I could not compile rich metadata for all issues scanned from 1913 to 1984, and instead capped it to 1913 to 1950. The scans from 1951 to 1984 instead are edited (cropped, colour correction, etc) and remain safely stored on Google Drive.

Figure 33: A typical .csv file containing a compilation of metadata for an issue (author's own image, 2021)

The metadata for *The Quarryman* issues consists of six fields: “Title”, “Source”, “Publisher”, “Rights”, “File”, and “Tags”. The “Title” describes the year of publication, along with the page number. The page number is significant, as each page would become an individual item, all grouped in a collection according to the year of publication. The “Source” and “Rights” refer to the Special Collections & Archives unit in UCC. “Publisher” provides contextual information of the publishing company that *The Quarryman* committee worked with. The “File” field is used for the mass uploading of .jpg files which corresponds to its relevant pages. “Tags” were used as a way of enabling searchability in the collection, as *The Quarryman* contained a plethora of rich contextual information detailing UCC’s social and academic culture, and Cork life. Here, I tried to find controlled vocabularies that I could adhere to during the compilation of my data. I referred to UNESCO (*UNESCO Thesaurus*, no date), however it was not as specific as needed for *The Quarryman*. The closest controlled vocabulary that would have suited the project was the Guidelines on Subject Access to Individual Works of Fiction, Drama, Etc. (GSAFD) (*Controlled*

Vocabularies | Librarians and Archivists | Library of Congress, no date). However, I ultimately decided to create my own standard because of the special nature of *The Quarryman*: a literary magazine which also contains puzzles, news, personal essays, and advertisements. It would be incredibly hard to find a suitable controlled vocabulary to use as a standard to describe *The Quarryman*'s contents.

Hence, I created broad tags which act as an umbrella encompassing more specific tags. For instance, a page containing an advertisement would include the “Advertisement” tag, alongside the advertiser’s name as another tag:

- Title** The Quarryman 1947: Page 13
- Source** Special Collections & Archives, UCC Library, University College Cork
- Publisher** The Kerryman, Tralee, Kerry
- Rights** Special Collections & Archives, UCC Library, University College Cork
- Collection** [The Quarryman 1947](#)
- Tags** [1947](#), [Advertisement](#), [Article](#), [Beamish](#)

Figure 34: A page from the 1947 issue (author’s own image, 2021)

In addition to this, instead of creating collections of each individual topic, users can explore a compilation of pages under a broader tag (“Advertisement”, “Clubs”, and “Societies” for instance), to more specific tags (such as “Beamish”, “Hurling”, and “Football”):

Browse Items (31 total)

Browse All **Browse by Tag** **Search Items**

Tags: **Philosoph**

Sort by: **Title** **Creator** **Date Added** ▾

The Quarryman 1950: Page 37	The Quarryman 1950: Page 36	The Quarryman 1948: Page 27	The Quarryman 1947: Page 57

Figure 35: Results shown with pages tagged with “Societies” (author’s own image, 2021)

Digital Archive: Platform

Omeka Classic fits the criteria of the project. Scheinfeldt (2010) states that Omeka’s “Technology Ecosystem” furthers cross-discipline collaboration, from Web CMS, to Library and Archival Repositories, and to Online Museum Collections and Exhibition Systems. Because of this, it is the ideal platform to host and display *The Quarryman*. Additionally, as a novice in website building, Omeka appears to be easy to navigate, and if there are any issues they can be solved quite quickly through a look on a search engine or the Omeka Forum:

Figure 36: Omeka Forum homepage (author's own image, 2021)

In the creation of the digital archive, I downloaded several plugins that I found to be potentially useful for displaying the issues and to assist me for easier uploading of .jpg files and metadata .csv files:

Plugin	Its purpose
Batch Uploader	Mass upload of files to Omeka.
COinS	Making item pages Zotero readable.
GDriveLinks Plugin	Links or embeds Google Drive documents in item views
PDF Embed	Embeds PDF files in item pages.
Simple Pages	Creates web pages for the website.

Universal Viewer	Integrates IIIF specifications and creates a virtual book in a unified player.
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Table 2: Plugins tested during the creation of the digital archive.

Batch Uploader

I used the Batch Uploader plugin for the mass uploading of metadata .csv files and .jpg files for *The Quarryman* issues. Initially there were some minor errors relating to the uploading, where a job would be frozen in one specific step. Fortunately, it was easily resolved after looking at relevant threads on the Omeka Forums. The plugin was convenient as it allowed users to upload files either in an existing collection or create a new collection. Additionally, its functionality extends to the mass uploading of files. Overall, this plugin did not require much of a learning curve and was very simple to use.

COinS

Adhering to “FAIRness” standards, the COinS plugin allows all items to be Zotero readable. This works well with the Google Chrome extension, Zotero Connect which saves web pages and online documents into one’s own Zotero account. When saving a item page from *The Quarryman* archive, the metadata fields from Omeka transfers directly to the corresponding or relevant fields on Zotero:

Item Type Document
Title The Quarryman 1945: Page 1
▼ Author (last), (first)
Abstract
Publisher The Kerryman, Tralee, Kerry
Date
Language
Short Title The Quarryman 1945
URL <https://quarryman.ivanxiang.net/items/show/701>

Figure 37: Metadata displayed in Zotero for a page from The Quarryman on the Omeka site (author's own image, 2021)

In addition to this, the plugin allows users to save multiple items at the same time when you are viewing a collection's items:

Figure 38: A pop-up window when using Zotero Connect on a collection web page (author's own image, 2021)

GDriveLinks

An issue I came across early on in this step of the project was how to properly present each issue's page individually. Tests were done to see whether a plugin would be most suitable. I

initially planned for one item to consist of multiple pages/files, so it would be a neater presentation.

I tested the GDriveLinks and PDF Embed plugin for the presentation of *The Quarryman* issues. The GDriveLinks plugin uses the URL field in each item as a means of embedding a file onto the item view page, from .jpg, .pdf, audio, and video files which are stored on Google Drive (*Omeka Classic - GDriveLinks Plugin*, 2020):

1929

Title 1929

URL

Figure 39: Embedded Google Drive .pdf file on an item view page (author's own image, 2021)

This plugin was considered because it meant that the files did not have to be uploaded onto the Omeka server. Each .pdf file size ranges from 60MB to 140 MB depending on the total number of pages, thus uploads took a very long amount of time to process, and I was wary of how much

storage would be required for the platform. Being able to host the files on a Google Drive with infinite storage would have resolved this issue. This plugin presents a unified look for all pages relating to a single issue, however there are a number of problems presented.

Referring back to the issues' .pdf file size again, its load time will prevent more users from accessing this collection, especially for those who do not have a fast internet connection. Because all pages are contained in a single item, I cannot present metadata for each individual page. Although this is an easy solution to present the issues' pages in a viewer, the issues' contents are not searchable.

PDF Embed

Figure 40: The PDF Embed viewer on an item view page (author's own image, 2021)

The PDF Embed plugin shares many similarities with the GDriveLinks plugin. This also includes the negatives of the load time associated with a large .pdf file and the inability to present metadata for each page displayed. The only difference between the two plugins is where the files are hosted. To use the PDF Embed plugin, the files must be uploaded onto the item's file section.

Both GDriveLinks and PDF Embed plugins could not satisfy the requirements of the project, especially the most important aspect of being able to present each individual file/page's associated metadata.

One item per issue

It appears that plugins may not necessarily solve this problem, thus I began to test how to best present the issues within Omeka's prebuilt system. Instead of having a singular .pdf file for each year of *The Quarryman*, I converted the file into individual .jpg files. Then, I uploaded all the .jpg files into one item:

1913

Title 1913

Citation "1913," *The Quarryman Journal 1913-1950*,
accessed August 27, 2021,
<https://quarryman.ivanxiang.net/items/show/926>

Figure 41: A single item with multiple files on Omeka (author's own image, 2021)

Similar to the plugins, I wanted a unified look of one item containing multiple pages because an issue itself is considered a single entity. Unfortunately, an item cannot have multiple metadata fields where you could assign to a file. Though it matched the project's requirement of having a gallery-style view for *The Quarryman* issues, this decision would render an unsearchable archive.

One collection with multiple items per issue

The next idea was to make a collection for each year's issue, with each individual page being entered into Omeka as its own item:

The Quarryman 1917

Title The Quarryman 1917

Description Vol. IV - No. 5 (March, 1917)

Items in the The Quarryman 1917 Collection

Figure 42: The 1917 issue, containing pages as items (author's own image, 2021)

While this was not ideal in my preference for a viewer to display all pages from one issue, this solution ultimately allowed each page to have its own metadata. It is not the “neatest” in terms of presentation, however the primary benefit to this solution is that all pages can be searchable now.

UniversalViewer: a compromise

The UniversalViewer plugin was used for a better viewing experience of the collections, in particular for users who would like to read through the pages in a viewer rather than clicking individually into an item's page:

View all 58 items

Figure 43: UniversalViewer displaying an item from the bottom of the 1945 issue's collection page (author's own image, 2021)

This was originally considered as a main viewer on an item page. It was ideal as the plugin provided an in-viewer tab for metadata on each item (*Omeka Classic - UniversalViewer*, 2015). However, the problem is related to my lack of coding experience. The placement of UniversalViewer is limited to the bottom of an item page, a collection page, or the “browse collections” page. Additionally, I did not have sufficient knowledge in configuring the placement of the UniversalViewer, alongside needing to remove my theme's default media viewer through coding. Hence, it was decided that the UniversalViewer plugin would be visible on a collection's page at the bottom, for users to browse through pages quickly.

Analysis & Discussion of Findings

This section features my overall experience of the digitisation of *The Quarryman* such as the challenges that had to be overcome during the project, alongside a discussion of what I believe

are the pros and cons associated with creating a digital archive on Omeka in terms of accessibility, reusability, and how it facilitates learning for researchers and readers.

Data Management Plan

Throughout the many processes in digitising *The Quarryman*, I found that in creating and following through a Data Management Plan resulted in better organisation of the project through its six sections:

1. **Data Collection:** This section made me address the importance of file formats, how I will produce it, and what efforts I must make in order to ensure it is as sustainable as possible for future researchers. Because of my lack of knowledge in file formats, this section provided me with issues that I had to research and consider properly. This assisted me in making key decisions to the file formatting: originally I believed .pdf files' high quality would be essential to preserving it as best as possible, but I shortly realised the downside of very large file sizes. Now, .tif files are used to preserve the issues, while .jpg files are uploaded to the Omeka site as a display copy.
2. **Documentation, Metadata & Data Quality:** Here, I was made to consider which fields to use in the metadata compilation, and how to best document the project. In doing so, I am making sure that this dissertation can act as a “blueprint” to future researchers. This section results in creating a more transparent documentation of the challenges and successes of the project.
3. **Data Storage & Backup:** The emphasis in data management and storage is essential to ensuring accessibility and sustainability of the project in the future. This segment of the plan led to my decision to use the Google Drive associated with my student email to store a copy of the dissertation, all the files created during the project (.pdf, .tif, and .jpg files)

as it will remain a stable cloud storage solution. All the relevant files are displayed in a public folder for those that would like to analyse *The Quarryman*, providing further access to the “behind the scenes” of the project.

4. Data Sharing & Long-Term Preservation: This section caused me to consider the appropriate digital repositories I could upload my data to. This led me to upload the project onto Zenodo, which will provide a means of discoverability and accessibility in a digital environment.
5. Data Management Responsibilities & Sourcing: I used this section as a way to consider all the possible software and equipment needed to undergo the project in the best possible manner. It guided me in choosing methods that are cost efficient which also aligns with the project’s aim of accessibility. Furthermore, it allowed me to give an estimate of each process of the project, such as scanning issues, editing, metadata compilation, and website building. Ultimately, this provided me with the ability to realistically envision the end goal of the project in accordance with my available resources, skills, and time.
6. Legal & Ethical Requirements: In preparation of the project, I began researching copyright as it was a major concern in the early stages of the project’s conception. The original scope of the project was to digitise both *The Quarryman* and the active publication *Quarryman*. Gaining access to digitise *Quarryman* appeared complicated. *Quarryman* is technically published by UCC, but distributed by English Literature Society, yet the editing committee was responsible for its printing. Furthermore, I may have had to contact each contributor for the rights to create a digital entity of their works. With the assistance of this section, I resolved this issue by choosing not to include *Quarryman*.

As A Novice Using Omeka

I believe that through my project, Omeka has proven itself to be a standard platform for archivists, librarians, and researchers alike in their endeavours of creating a digital exhibition, collections, and or archive. The platform's adherence to Dublin Core standards made it much easier for me to ensure accessibility as it aligns with FAIR data standards, too. As a novice in Content Management Systems, I thought Omeka would require a steep learning curve before I could create a solid digital archive to host and display *The Quarryman*. However, I soon realised how easy Omeka was to use. Because of Reclaim Hosting, creating an Omeka site was frictionless as it did not require any manual installation from the user. Installing plugins to the platform was relatively easy as well because of the easy layout of Reclaim Hosting's File Manager. Plugins such as Batch Uploader made the digitisation process even easier as it allowed mass uploads of both metadata compilations and the files itself. I commend Omeka for being an effortless platform to navigate from uploading files, to configuring themes, and to displaying items. Omeka is cost efficient (free!) and certainly manageable for even those who are not up to date in technology. This accessibility results in a wider user base, which ultimately opens up more projects in digital preserving cultural items of importance. Institutions as small as local small town libraries, to student researchers, to larger organisations are all able to avail of such a powerful tool as long as they have a computer with internet access. Omeka's Dublin Core standards also means that small institutions who may lack understanding of its importance can still ensure sustainability, even if unknowingly.

Web Accessibility

In the creation of the Omeka site, I referred to WAI and UDL principles to provide a more accessible way of navigating and presenting *The Quarryman* to be inclusive of all potential users. The primary colours of the theme were bright yellow, white, and black. The theme's high contrast typography and its simplicity of using three colours is accessible to those with intellectual disabilities such as dyslexia. Additionally, the high contrast also functions as a visually bold aesthetic. The zoom feature is present in both the item view page and the UniversalViewer plugin in the footer of the browse view collection page. While this provides a chance for users to view the pages much closer, it also is accessible to those with viewing impairments.

However, there are areas in the site that could have been improved for accessibility to users. A lot of clicking is required to navigate through the collections, and even between pages in an issue. In the item view page, users must click the page to enable a closer view of the page, otherwise it is rather small and unreadable. Additionally, there is not a function which allows viewers to read all pages from an issue in a seamless manner. Through the item view page, users can click on "next item" to view the next page, however there are a lot of processes associated with what should be simple browsing. The UniversalViewer plugin is the closest to creating a more accessible experience as it displays all pages in a collection in the index tab of the viewer. Unfortunately, for the sake of creating metadata for each individual page, all pages cannot be contained in one item. This ultimately results in the UniversalViewer plugin to display pages individually, instead of being able to view it as a gallery:

Figure 44: UniversalViewer displaying individual pages (source: author's own image, 2021)

Being able to code the viewer into a gallery is a small, yet significant detail to facilitate more immersion for viewers, however as a novice website builder, it was unfortunate that it is out of my scope as of writing.

An Abundance of Tags

After I uploaded all metadata .csv files to the Omeka site, it became apparent how many tags I had created in the process of enabling searchability of the collection. The benefit of the theme chosen for the Omeka site is that the words in the “search by Tags” section is larger or smaller according to its frequency in being used, which is a simple and visual method of displaying its prevalence in *The Quarryman*. However, the downside to this is that it can be considered as information overload in the form of a visual “clutter” which is not entirely accessible to all users, especially those with intellectual disabilities such as dyslexia and autism. With a total of 192 unique Tags on the site, it would have been beneficial to either omit some tags, or sort tags into expandable categories. For example, the Advertisements tag can be used as an umbrella term, but

once expanded users can refine into specific tags assigned to their respective advertiser. I could not provide a solution as I am not technically competent enough here, but this issue is certainly acknowledged.

Neatline: A Missed Opportunity?

In the scanning process and even during the compilation of metadata for *The Quarryman*, I realised the potential of further cultural enrichment contained within the magazine's pages. After *The Quarryman's* digitisation, I find myself beginning to take notice of the names of stores around Cork City in my personal time. Through the advertisements of *The Quarryman*, the evolution of Cork as a city is also preserved in the form of textual documentation. Commercial buildings become a cultural landmark of sorts as a fragment of Cork City from the past. For instance, Johnson & Perrott is a car dealership that continues its trading today since 1810 (*About Us | Johnson and Perrott Motor Group Cork*, no date). The 1913 to 1950 issues also document the evolution of businesses, such as The Gresham Hotel which is now more commonly known as The Metropole Hotel. For the businesses that do not survive in a contemporary time, it preserves their memory for newer, younger generations and for those that are not Cork City natives. A thriving dance hall from the 1920s to the nineties, Arcadia is better known as The Arc by goers of the past (*The Arcadia*, 2017). What currently stands in place of this cultural landmark are now apartment blocks with "hall of fame" like star tiles in the front of the building. I have lived in these apartment blocks myself, and I believe that others like me would not have realised its cultural significance without the help and access to resources in the form of digital collections. I find that I missed a large opportunity in this project to raise awareness of these cultural spaces in the past. It will be a useful endeavour in the future to investigate using the Neatline plugin on Omeka to appoint geospatial mappings of these spaces, regardless if these businesses continue

trading or are no longer active. This would allow older users to envision a nostalgic Cork, while providing younger users to explore the history behind the stores we see today. I had originally planned to use Neatline for the project, however, at the time I did not know what it could have been used for. Perhaps if I had more time to reflect like I have here earlier in the process of the project I would have provided another substantial resource as part of the digital archive of *The Quarryman*.

Copyright, Ownership, and Repositories

The Data Management Plan contains a section regarding depositing into a digital repository. Uploading to Europeana and or the Digital Repository of Ireland was always the intention of the project in its early conception. By uploading to Europeana or DRI, it has extreme potential to elevate the sustainability of the project and provide exposure to the valuable textual information in *The Quarryman*'s issues. The project's aim to adhere to FAIR data standards had another motive behind it - it would allow all the data created to be easily transferable into these repositories. However, I refrained from doing so because of my concerns with copyright. *The Quarryman* is currently held in UCC's Special Collections & Archives unit, meaning that all rights belong to the university. Though I have copyright clearance to scan, digitise, and scan these issues for the purposes of research, *The Quarryman* as a digital entity is a grey zone, I believe. Who owns the rights to *The Quarryman* as a digital entity? Is it me, as a creator of its scans, its metadata, and its management? Or does it still remain to be a property of the institution? Undoubtedly, scans are technically digital images, but it needs more governance. What is the difference between these scans and someone simply taking a picture of a quote from their favourite book?

Conclusion

The completion of this project has provided me with an in-depth insight into the efforts that are required to create a solid digital archive. The original scope of the project was to fully digitise an issue from every year between 1913 to 1984. Now that I can reflect on the earlier stages of the project, I realise how ambitious it was to believe that I could possibly digitise <2,000 items. This project provided me with an appreciation towards digital archivists, librarians, and digitisation teams in the GLAM industry for preserving cultural heritage. Digitising *The Quarryman* was intensive at times, due to having to provide metadata for approximately 800 files. This workload had already been cut in half as I did not continue the digitisation of issues beyond 1950. Overall, the scanning, editing, metadata compiling, and uploading of items took at least 80-100 hours; there is no denying that digitisation takes a lot of time and effort! While it would have been ideal to fully digitise the issues available, I believe that the current digitised collections can still be a valuable educational and cultural resource for users and researchers alike.

This project proves that accessibility and inclusivity can be achieved without any cost. I did not have to purchase any digital tool or equipment - all software used during the project were either freeware or open-sourced programmes. We must not underestimate the power and potential behind volunteers who contribute towards valuable resources which are freely open to use for all. However, I must acknowledge my privilege as a student in a higher education institution. With these credentials, I could avail of important and high quality equipment in the Special Collections & Archives unit, whereas others outside of the institution may have had to use monetary resources to scan their objects.

Presently, the “leftovers” of the project remain safely stored in Google Drive. I believe that through following the principles of FAIR data, *The Quarryman* digital archive has a high potential to become fully completed in the future. Preserving these issues beyond UCC’s Special Collections & Archives unit is a benefit of many parties: UCC Library, *Quarryman*’s committee, the School of English, the English Literature Society, and the Cork Folklore Project. The project ultimately reclaims a digital space for literary scene in UCC, while facilitating engagement and promotion of *Quarryman* and its historical importance in the sphere of UCC and the wider Cork community.

The future of this project is ultimately in the hands of those who want to continue the digitisation of *The Quarryman*. I believe that there are a number of benefits to digitising *Quarryman*, too. Perhaps a collaborative effort with *Quarryman*’s committee will be another step into ensuring that the past and present is well documented, preserved and accessible to all. If *Quarryman* were to be digitised as well, it can encapsulate our present cultural climate in UCC and the greater Cork region, alongside with the textual documentation the continuous growth of UCC as a historical and academic institution through its student population, alumni, and faculty.

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